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**COMPARATIVE STUDY ON ANXIETY LEVEL BETWEEN BOYS AND
GIRLS FOOTBALL PLAYERS**

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present study was to find out the anxiety level between boys and girls football players. 60 football players (30 boys and 30 girls) were selected from Subroto Mukherjee football tournament 2015 held at Khuman Lampak Sports Complex for the study. The average age of the players is 16.5 years. The sample of the study has been selected randomly. Hypotheses of the present study were Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores of Boys and Girls football players would be high and there will be no significant difference on Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores between boys and girls football players. Sports competitive Anxiety Test (SCAT) by (Martens et al., 1990) was used to measure the level of anxiety for the football players. The Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores of Boys and Girls football players was found to be average ($n=60$, $mean=198.58$, $\sigma= 2.92$ and $SEM =0.37$). Difference on Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores between Boys ($n=30$, $mean=18.46$, $\sigma=2.30$) and Girls ($n=30$, $mean=18.70$, $\sigma=3.47$) football players was found to be statistically not significant at $p\leq 0.05$ ($t\text{-value}=0.760$) at $df=78$. The current study was limited in sample size, tools adopted, and variables undertaken for the study. Further research can be done with larger sample size and also on different age group.

Keywords:

Anxiety, Boys, Girls, Football, SCAT.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the games and sports, psychological and physiological factors play an important role in determining the performance level (Grange & Kerr, 2010; Schilling & Hyashi, 2001). It has been recognized for many years that psychological factors, in particular anxiety, play an important role in competition. (Lizuka, 2005) observed as a result of his study that many factors, such as expectations, perfectionism, fear of failure, lack of confidence include feelings of anxiety in athletes. Those athletes, who experience high levels of anxiety, may fall sick, muscle tension, show aggressive behaviours face sleeping problems, low self- confidence and drop out of sport (Cox, 2010; Weinberg & Gould, 2010; Abel & Larkin, 1990).

Anxiety which is seen as an important determinant of performance in sports environments has been defined in many ways by authors. As to Anshel “Anxiety is a perceived threat”. It is seen in two forms. The first one is trait anxiety which is a part of behavioural patterns of individuals. The latter is state anxiety. Anxiety before or during athletic competitions can hinder your performance as an athlete. The coordinated movement required by athletic events becomes increasingly difficult when your body is in a tense state. A certain level of physical arousal is helpful and prepares us for competition. But when the physical symptoms of anxiety are too great, they may seriously interfere with your ability to compete. Similarly, a certain amount of worry about how you perform can be helpful in competition, but severe cognitive symptoms of anxiety such as negative thought patterns and expectations of failure can bring about a self- fulfilling prophecy. If there is a substantial difference between how you perform during competitions, anxiety may be affecting your performance (Nileshkumar, 2012). Anxiety may be positive motivation force or it may interfere with successful athletic performances. As a positive motivating force it can be instrumental in motivating the athlete to work harder to find new and better ways to improve performances and to help set goals. The athletic skills and his self-confidence as a negative motivator anxiety may interfere with productive as well as constructive thinking. Athletes may attempt to handle anxiety by denying the need to work hard. This can lead to development of poor work habits or athletic technique. These often lead to failure and, in turn, lack of confidence and increased anxiety.

Competitive Anxiety in Sport concludes with a theory of competitive anxiety based on an interaction between uncertainty about the outcome and the importance assigned to that outcome. Anxiety before or during athletic competitions can hinder performance of an athlete. The coordinated movement required by athletic events becomes increasingly difficult when your body is in a tense state. A certain level of physical arousal is helpful and prepares us for competition. But when the physical symptoms of anxiety are too great, they may seriously interfere with your ability to compete. Similarly, a certain amount of worry about how you perform can be helpful in competition, but severe cognitive symptoms of anxiety such as negative thought patterns and expectations of failure can bring about a self-fulfilling prophecy. If there is a substantial difference between how you perform during practice and how you do during competitions, anxiety may be affecting your performance. (Khan and Khan, 2014)

The title of the problem for the present study is stated as “*Comparative Study on Anxiety Level between Boys and Girls Football Players*”

The objectives of the present study was to find out the sports competitive anxiety test scores of Boys and Girls football players and to find out if there exists any difference on the sports competitive anxiety test scores between Boys and Girls Football players.

The following hypotheses was framed for the present study

Hypothesis 1: The Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores of Boys and Girls football players would be high.

Hypothesis 2: there will be no significant difference on Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores between Boys and Girls Football Players.

2. METHODS

SELECTION OF SUBJECTS

For the purpose of the study, 60 football players (30 boys and 30 girls) who took part in Subroto Mukherjee football tournament for under 17 boys and girls held at Khuman Lampak Sports Complex from 13th to 19th June 2015 were selected randomly from the participating teams. The average age of the participants was 16.5 years.

SELECTION OF TOOLS

Sports competitive Anxiety Test (SCAT) by (Martens et al., 1990) was used to measure the level of anxiety for the football players. This test is composed of 15 items on 3-point scale which include 5 spurious items, 8 positive items and 2 negative items. And, as such the maximum possible score on the SCAT was 30. The summated scores on each items on the scale formed the Sports Competitive Anxiety Test scores. Norms for interpretation of the results has been shown below:

SCAT Score	Verbal Interpretation
Less than 17	Low level of Sports Competitive Anxiety
17 to 24	Average level of Sports Competitive Anxiety
More than 24	High level of Sports Competitive Anxiety

DATA COLLECTION

The data were collected from the players during the competition before collection of data proper instruction was given to them so that accurate response can be obtain from them.

STATISTICAL TOOLS

Statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, standard error of mean, and t-test has been employed in the present study. The level of significance chosen was .05.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis 1: The Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores of Boys and Girls football players would be high.

Table 1: SCAT Scores of Boys and Girls Football players

N	Mean	Standard Deviation(σ)	Standard Error of Mean
60	18.58	2.92	0.37

The Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores of Boys and Girls football players was found to be average ($n=60$, mean=198.58, $\sigma= 2.92$ and $SE_M =0.37$). It was anticipated that the Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores would be high.

Thus, the hypothesis that “The Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores of Boys and Girls football players would be high” fails to be accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There will be no significant difference on Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores between Boys and Girls football Players.

Table 2: Mean values and comparison of Sports Competitive Anxiety between Boys and Girls Football Players

Sex	N	Mean	σ	SEm	df	t- value
Boys	30	18.46	2.30	0.42	58	0.760
Girls	30	18.70	3.47	0.63		

Difference on Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores between Boys (n=30, mean=18.46, σ =2.30) and Girls (n=30, mean=18.70, σ =3.47) football players was found to be statistically not significant at $p \leq 0.05$ t-value=0.760 at df=78.

Thus, the hypothesis “There is no significant difference on Sports Competitive Anxiety Scores between Boys and Girls football players” was accepted.

Mean scores of Anxiety between Boys and Girls are depicted graphically in fig 1.

Figure 1: The Graphical Representation of Mean Scores of Anxiety between Boys and Girls Football Players

The study revealed that boys and girls football players have average level of anxiety and there exist no significant difference between boys and girls football players on anxiety. Similar findings were also reported by some studies e. g. Amit K. Gamit (2013), M.N. Singh et al., (2013). The finding of the present study was found to be refuting with some others studies e.g. Quadri Syed Javed (2013) who found that girls players have more anxiety level than boys players.

It may therefore be construed that the Sports Competitive Anxiety of boys and girls football players was average and sex may not be a determining variable for Sports Competitive Anxiety.

4. CONCLUSION

The finding of the study reveals that Sports Competitive Anxiety of boys and girls football players was average and there exists no significant difference on SCAT Score between Boys and Girls football players.

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